

IS RENEWABLE ENERGY AN ENABLER OR INHIBITOR OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGS)?

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ABSTRACT

A noticeable fact witnessable from the impact of global warming is that the most of the countries in the world are targeting to achieve 100% renewable energy by 2050. In this regard, progressive impact of renewable energy can be seen on the world energy sector. But its positive effect is yet to be found in proper sense in the attainment of sustainable development goals (SDGs). The sustainable development goals are divided in three groups, namely, environment, society and economy out of total of 17 SDGs. In 169 targets set in SDGs, the exponential growth of renewable energy is yet to make its true imprint visible in the course of sustainable development. It requires sensible planning and constructive action plan in support it. A shift towards renewable energy is inevitably occurred due to adverse effect already being caused by conventional energy sources such as coal, oil and natural gas. In this paper an analysis is made relying various research work done in this behalf as to know how renewable energy would make its impact both in positive and negative sense in the achievements of SDGs.

Keywords

Sustainable Development Goals, renewable energy, targets of SDGs, utilization of renewable energy, impact analysis

INTRODUCTION

Every country has considered energy as an absolute necessity for its development. But issues concerning the utilization and supply of energy derived, especially from conventional energy sources have become a cause for global warming and environmental challenges such as depletion of ozone, destruction of forest, acid precipitation, wildlife loss, emission of radioactive, pollution of water, air and land¹. It has in turn reduced the use of conventional energy sources. In its use, renewable energy such as wind, solar, photovoltaic, hydropower etc have been set in.² This option has been preferred to achieve environmentally sound technology with low electricity cost, creation of job, improvisation of health, community development of rural areas existing particularly in developing countries and prominently to make world free from carbonisation in coming days.³ By 2020, the total installed capacity of

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¹Salim H.K., Padfield K., Hansen S.B., Mohamad S.E., Yuzir A., Syayuti K., et al. Global trends in environmental management system and ISO14001 research, J. cleaner prod., 170 (2018), PP. 645-653

²Ediger V.S., An integrated review and analysis of multi-energy transition from fossil fuels to renewables. Energy Procedia, 156 (2019), PP. 2-6.

³Kumar M. Social, Economic and Environmental impacts of Renewable Energy Resources. Intech Open, Wind Solar Hybrid Renewable Energy System I, (2020)

renewable energy grew almost 10% to reach 2839 GW.⁴ Two-third growth in renewable energy has mainly come from solar PV and wind. In 2021, the share of renewables, in the generation of electricity have reached all time high of 30% due to prominence being given to generate electricity from renewable resources.⁵

Measures along with supporting strategies to reduce adverse environmental impacts and optimal operation of renewable energy sources are being stressed in different part of the world⁶. Along with-it back-up steps such as encouragement to improve of reliability, safety of energy use, reduction of cost, increase in energy efficiency, expansion of market for renewable energy, improvisation in integration of micro-organism, smart grid and accurate predictions as to renewable energy production⁷ are infused into service. But it has become important to take proper care while utilising renewable energy along with targets being set in the form of SDGs. If it is not taken care of, it will lead to imbalance in pushing three main elements such as environment, society and economy in parallel manner

INTERFACE BETWEEN SDGS AND RENEWABLE ENERGY

SDGs provide a solid perspective and reflection on a path that lie ahead on all aspects of sustainability. The energy works out as a key linking element to sustainability such as poverty eradication, gender equality, climate action, food security, health, education, sustainable cities and transport. It ensures equal participation of women on the one hand and makes the society at large benefitted from it on the other hand. Human development is directly related to access to energy. Women in particular in rural areas spend more time in collecting fuel, water and preparing meals. As access to energy would allow them to utilize the saved time for education and other constructive works. An exposure to quality education would make them entitled to have equal pay, equal treatment and equal status.

In the first target of 7th goal of SDGS, there is a necessity of ensuring universal access to affordable, reliable and modern energy sources by 2030. In the second target of 7th goal of SDGs, the relevancy of increasing the share of renewable energy in substantial portion in the global energy mix by 2030 is signified. In the third target of 7th goal of SDGs, a measure to double the global rate of energy efficiency is highlighted. The energy efficiency is to be

⁴Global Status Report, Renewables 2021, Global Status Report-REN21

⁵International Energy Agency (IEA) Renewables-Global Energy Review 2021-Analysis-IEA (2021)

⁶Zahraee S., Assadi M.K., Saidur R.m Application of artificial intelligence methods for hybrid energy system optimization. *renew. Sustain. Energy. Rev.*, 6,6 (2016), PP. 617-630

⁷ibid

made achievable by 2030 providing suitable financial incentives by the governments and access to information as to energy efficiency to people. In clause (a) target of 7th goal of SDGs sets to enhance international co-operation to energy efficiency, advancement made in availing cleaner fossil fuel technology, promotes investment towards in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology. It would act as supportive measure to get international financial flows to involve in research and development of clean energy and renewable energy production with hybrid system. An investment in global energy access for electrification and in the availment of clean energy would help to achieve SDGs by 2030.

In the clause (b) target of 7th goal of SDGs, an aim to expand infrastructure and upgrade technology for supplying modern and sustainable energy services for developing countries, the least developed countries, in particular small island developing states and landlocked developing countries in accordance with their respective programmes supportis set to be by 2030.

IMPACT RENEWABLE ENERGY UTILIZATION ON ENVIRONMENT

The use of renewable energy has limited negative impact. The ability of renewable energy in reducing Green House Gas replacing traditional fuel to achieve 50% of target set in 13th goal of SDGs and 25% target aimed in 14th goal of SDGs⁸. In the targets aimed in 13.1 and 13.2 of SDGs obligate the countries to identify climate related hazards and to incorporate action by way of national strategies and planning to address the climate change⁹. The plan published by US confirm that approximately 70% of carbon di oxide emission would reduce on use of renewable energy by 2050¹⁰. Even Reports published in New Zealand and Europe¹¹ establish it.

The construction of wind turbine being carried-out showed negligible effects on forests, fauna and flora, migratory birds' pathways. It signifies thatrenewable energy is consistent with targe set in15th goal of SDGs. The continuous development of renewable sources would

⁸Salaun K., Cerda E., Climate change impacts on renewable energy generation. A review of quantitative projects Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev., 116 (2019), Article 109415

⁹ibid

¹⁰ Khanna N.Z., Zhou N., Fridley D., KE J. Qualifying the potential impacts of China's power-sector policies on coal input and CO₂ emissions through 2050: A bottom-up perspective *Util. Policy*, 41 (2016), PP. 128-138

¹¹Walmsley M.R., Walmsley T.G., Atkins M.J., Kamp P.J., Neale J.R., Minimising carbon emissions and energy expended for electricity generation in New Zealand through to 2050. *Appl. Energy*, 135 (2014), PP. 656-665

help to minimize some kind of air pollutions¹², reduce the effects of ocean acidifications¹³ and stabilise benefits accruable from ecosystem such as life, land, water and forests.¹⁴

The renewable energy development does have a negative effect when it is used as a tidal energy because it inhibits target set in 15.4 of SDGs. The establishment of tidal energy in coastal estuaries or bays of tidal barrage would cause significant ecological effects on bird feeding areas¹⁵. Wave energy and offshore tidal steam energy collectors holding configurations with moving part would cause complex possible environmental impacts for each device category¹⁶.

Under the target set in 14.2 of SDGs, there is a potentiality to use renewable energy to produce clean energy and to protect, consume marine's system sustaining marine system environment. The use of renewable energy in marine system would assist in reducing anthropogenic CO₂ emission. It would achieve productive ocean by providing protection against sea environment change¹⁷. But these potential positive effects are marred by negative effect in achieving the target set in 14.2 SDGs such as increase in underwater noise, collision risk and electromagnetic field emission¹⁸.

The establishment of the large-scale wind farm¹⁹ and solar energy²⁰ in large space in some countries would lead to the cutting of trees and encroachment of agricultural land in larger ways.

It is in the context of achievement of target set in 15.1, 15.2 and 15.11 of SDGs, it would act as an inhibitor. It would cause harm to forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands. It would

¹²Alvare Z-Harranz A., Balsalobre-Lorente D., Shahbaz M., Caortas J.M., Energy Innovation and renewable energy consumption in the correction of air pollution levels. *Energy Policy*, 105 (2017), PP. 386-397

¹³Clements J. C., Chepin. T., Ocean acidification and marine aquaculture in north America: Potential impacts and mitigation strategies. *Rev. Aquac.*, 9 (2017), PP. 326-341

¹⁴Oakleap J.R., Kennedy C.M., Baruch-Mordo S., Gerber J.S., West P.C., Johnson J. A., et al. Mapping global development. Potential for renewable energy; fossil fuels; mining and agriculture sectors. *Sci. Data*, 6 (2019), PP. 1-17

¹⁵Frid G., Andonegi E., Depestele J., Judd A., Rogers S. I., et al. The environmental interactions of tidal and wave energy generation devices. *Environ. Impact Assess. Rev.* 32, (2012), PP. 133-139

¹⁶Lin L., Yu H., Offshore wave energy generation devices: impacts on ocean bio-environment. *Acta Ecol. Sin.*, 32 (2012), PP. 117-122

¹⁷Will steed E., Gill A. B., Birchenough S. N., Jude S., Assessing the cumulative environmental effects of marine renewable energy developments: Establishing common ground. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 577 (2017), PP. 19-32

¹⁸ibid

¹⁹Schuster E.m Balling L., Koppel J., Consolidating the state Knowledge: a synoptical review of wind energy's wildlife effects. *Environ. Manag.*, 56 (2015), PP. 300-331

²⁰Turney. D., Fthenakins V. Environmental impactgs from the installation and operation of large scale solar power plants. *Renew. Sustain. Energy, Rev.*, 15 (2011), PP. 3261-3270

provide greater pathways to hydropower and bioenergy than wind, solar, geothermal and ocean²¹. It would cause trade-off with some bio-diversity especially when there would be large scale distribution of renewable energy²².

IMPACT OF RENEWABLE ENERGY UTILIZATION ON SOCIETY

Renewable energy plays its prime role in positive sense even on the society's well-being. The improvement in the operation, efficiency and development of renewable energy would provide an opportunity to reduce energy costs and emissions. By 2050, the cost to be incurred for renewable energy production would be much better than non-renewable energy²³. The substantial fulfilment of target set in 7.2 SDGs would indicate boosting of renewable in the global energy mix. The generation capacity of renewable energy in 2018 was just 1 GW in 10 countries. But it has now exceeded 10GW of capacity in 30 countries across the globe²⁴. Renewable energy has been contributing to achieve targets set in goal 4 of SDGs by providing broader energy access helpful to ensure and promote equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities to all. The continuous growth of renewable energy would help in creation of jobs and speeding up economic development²⁵. The factories and industries equipped with renewable energy prospectus would provide income generating activities to several youth and adults²⁶. Its impact could be found in jobs because the energy made available from it is local in nature and is accessible without heavy infrastructure²⁷. Along with job opportunities at the local level, the development of renewable energy assists in improving health and consumer choice. Renewable energy has given an option to use solar PV energy or hybrid energy to pump the water from the underground wells in the rural²⁸ and

²¹Gasparates A., Doll C.N., Estebon M., Ahmed A., Olang T.A., Renewable energy and biodiversity: Implications for transitioning to a Green Economy. *Renew. Sustain. Energy. Rev.*, 70 (2017), PP. 161-184

²²ibid

²³Ivanovski K., Hailemariam A., Smyth R., The effect of renewable and non-renewable energy consumption on economic growth: Non-Parametric evidence. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 286 (2021), Article 124956

²⁴Supra note 6

²⁵ibid

²⁶Wei M., Patadia S., Kammen D. M., Putting renewables and energy efficiency to work: How many jobs can the clean energy industry generate in the US? *Energy Policy*, 38 (2010), PP. 919-931

²⁷Colombo E., Romeo F., Mattarolo L., Barbieri J., Morozzo M., An impact evaluation framework based on sustainable livelihood for energy development projects: An application to ethopia.

²⁸Barron-Hafford G.A., Pavao-Auckerman M.A., Minor R.L., Sutter L.F., Barnett-Moreno I., Blackett D.T., et al. Agrivoltaics provide mutual benefits across the food energy-water nexus in drylands. *Nat. sustain.*, 2 (2019), PP. 848-855

desert areas²⁹. This option has decreased the number of people suffering from water shortages. The advancement being done in renewable energy has helped to achieve the target set in 6.4 of SDGs.

As per the report of the World Health Organisation around 760 million people in the world do not have an access to clean drinking water³⁰. They face water scarcity not due to water drought but on account of off-grid supply of energy, remoteness and high solar irradiation. A submersible water pump which is equipped stand alone or hybrid PV and wind energy would provide continuous power in an effective manner.³¹

Renewable energy would become inhibitor while achieving target set in SDGs 1.2, 1.4, 3.9, 4.4, 4.9, 6.6, 11.1, 11.8 and 16.2. especially while utilizing it in the form of biomass does not assist in decreasing disease and preventing death caused from toxic substances and pollutants being released to in the air water and soil³². Carbon monoxide being released from Biomass energy would cause headaches, nausea, dizziness³³. Its high concentration would even lead to premature death³⁴. The installation of renewable energy farm constructed in the form of solar, wind, biomass, hydropower in large scale would cause problems relating to water-based ecosystem such as forest, wetlands and mountain valley³⁵. It would upset the target set in 6.6 of SDGs, because the operation of biomass energy and installation of solar and wind farms would permit cutting of tree for wood and utilizing of wet land³⁶. However, its significance cannot be sidelined considering supportive elements lying in it in relation to the achievement of targets³⁷ laid down in SDGs 2,5 and 7.

IMPACT OF RENEWABLE ENERGY UTILIZATION ON ECONOMY

²⁹Bertsiou M., Feloni E., Karpouzou D., Baltas E., Water management and electricity output of a hybrid renewable energy system (HREs) in fournoi island in Aegean sea. *Renew. Energy*, 118 (2018), PP. 790-798

³⁰Bowen T., Ninno C., Andrews G., Coll-Black S., Gentilini U., Johnson K., et al. 2020. International Energy Agency; United Nations Statistics Division; World Bank; World Health Organisation. Policy, books. Google.com

³¹Freire Gormaly M., Experimental characterization of membrane fouling under intermittent operation and its application to the optimization of solar photovoltaic powered reverse osmosis drinking water treatment systems, (2018), search.Proquest.com

³²Subramanian M. Deadly dinners. *Nature*, 509 (2014), P. 548

³³ibid

³⁴ibid

³⁵Supra note 23

³⁶Ibid

³⁷Drechsler M., Egerer J., Hange M., Masurowski F., Meyerhoff J., Oehlmann M., Efficient and equitable spatial allocation of renewable power plants at the country scale *Nat. energy*, 2 (2017), P. 17124

Renewable energy assist in achieving economic targets set in SDGs in 8, 9, 10, 12 and 17. Around 60 targets would fall within economic group. Out of which 30 targets, i.e., 50% of target could be achieved by the use of renewable energy³⁸.

Renewable energy provides an option to have labour service from local communities, materials from local area and services from local owners or banks or enterprises. It would facilitate local communities to set-up a trust fund of their own and invest the income generated from the sale of energy for the benefits of locals. An increase in the deployment of renewable energy would result in creation of more job opportunities and a growth in jobs from few thousand to more than one million by 2030³⁹. The creation of jobs by renewable energy would compensate the loss of jobs in fossil fuel's sectors. The number of jobs created in solar PV is twice the number of jobs being created in coal or natural gas energy sector⁴⁰. It would have a positive impact in achieving the targets set in SDGs. The report being given by IRENA 2016, would indicate positive signals as to the growth of job from the utilization and deployment of renewable energy in different parts of the world⁴¹. The supply chain involved in renewable energy indicates that its expansion seems to be more dispersed and labour intensive in nature in comparison with the traditional energy market⁴². Targets set in 8.3 SDGs could be achieved by using the benefits accruable from renewable energy.

Renewable energy provides considerable scope for the enhancement of small and micro enterprise. The use of bio gas and hydropower especially in rural areas would be helpful in achieving the targets set in 9.3 of SDGs⁴³. It would strengthen domestic resources mobilization because of wide spread application of diversified resources available in the course of generation of electricity from renewable energy. It would allow a country to achieve the target set in 17th goal of SDGs by strengthening the means of implementation

³⁸Supra note 32

³⁹Ferroukhi R., Lopez-Pena A, Kieffer G., Nagpal D., Hawila D., Khalid A., et al. Renewable Energy Benefits: Measuring the Economics. International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), Abu Dhabi (2016)

⁴⁰Essletzbichler J. Renewable energy technology and path creation: A multi-scalar approach to energy transition in the UK. Eur. Plann. Stud., 20 (2012) PP.799-816

⁴¹IRENA Renewable Energy Benefits: Measuring the Economics. International Renewable Energy Agency Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates (2016)

⁴²Supra note 42

⁴³Pfeiffer B., Mulder P., Explaining the diffusion of renewable energy technology in developing countries. Energy Econ., 40 (2013), PP. 285- 296

revitalization of the global partnership⁴⁴. The developing countries have already encouraged the organisations to establish PV power plants in rural and remote areas. It has helped the countries to give preference to renewable energy offering a new policy of tax on the use of renewable energy technology that would act as an encouragement for investment not just to companies and even to individuals⁴⁵. It has given further boost for global partnership for sustainable development in renewable energy sector in terms of research, financial support and economic aspect⁴⁶.

But use of marine, renewable energy would cause negative effect in economic groups targeted in SDGs 6. Its use would be detrimental to environment by way of collision, habitat destruction, noise pollution in utilization of electromagnetic devices in the course of generation of renewable energy⁴⁷.

EXTENT OF SUSTAINABILITY OF RENEWABLE ENERGY UTILIZATION

A wide variety of goals set in SDGs has move the countries to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy in the process of advancement of economic growth, environment of energy security, access to electricity and alleviation of climate change⁴⁸. Its analysis depicts that renewable has given an option to the countries to achieve 100% target in respect of 7th goal of SDG i.e., providing of affordable and clean energy to the community at large⁴⁹. But there are limitations over the attainment of 100% sustainability utilizing renewable energy. An analysis done in this regard indicates that 13% of the global population does not have an access to modern energy⁵⁰. Even in UN report given in this behalf points-out that one in several people is yet to have electricity⁵¹. World Bank note in this regard exhibits that people who live in the

⁴⁴ Surana K., Anadon L.D., Public Policy and financial resources mobilization for wind energy in developing countries: a comparison of approaches and outcomes in China and India. *Global Environ. Change*, 35 (2015), Pp. 340-359

⁴⁵ Freire-Gonzalez J., Puigventosa I., Reformulating taxes for an energy transition *Energy Econ.*, 78 (2019), PP. 312-323

⁴⁶ Eitan A., Herman L., Fischhendler I., Rosen G., Community-Private Sector Partnership in renewable energy. *Renew. Sustain. Energy. Rev.* 105 (2019), PP. 95-104

⁴⁷ Shields M.A., Woolf D.K., Grist P., Kerr S.A., Jackson A.G., Harris R.E., et al. Marine renewable energy: The ecological implications of the marine environment. *Ocean coast. Manag.*, 54 (2011), PP. 2-9

⁴⁸ Lund H., Renewable energy strategies for sustainable development. *Energy*, 32 (2007), PP. 912-919

⁴⁹ *ibid*

⁵⁰ Rehman A., The nexus of electricity access, population growth in Pakistan and projection through, 2040, *Int. J. Energy sector. Manag* (2019), emerald.com

⁵¹ UN SDG. Sustainable development goal 7 1 SDG7 affordable and clean energy (2019)

developing rural areas are facing the unavailability of electricity⁵². In order to fill the energy gap, it is essential to generate renewable energy as per theoretically estimated level.

The utilization of sources of renewable energy would help to achieve many targets being set in 17SDGs with multiple benefits such as job creation, energy security, economic prospectus, meet environmental safety and prevention of global warming⁵³. In economic support derivable from the utilization of renewable energy, it is not clearly visible in the reports so far presented in this behalf because reports analysed concerning the targets set in 8th SDGs do not make note worthy link between the consumption of renewable and total factor of productivity⁵⁴. There lies a contrast in renewable utilization, i.e., its consumption endangers favourable externality that leads to economic growth⁵⁵. Renewable energy sources are yet to provide secure, reliable and economic integration into existing electrical grid because it has not attained unique standard required for it⁵⁶.

The strategies so far adopted for the utilization of renewable energy are to be concretised to balance four elements such as environment protection⁵⁷. The studies done in this regard have shown that the use of renewable energy in the form of biomass though hold advantages in some respect, it has been releasing carbon monoxide and causing headache, dizziness, nausea and premature death and acting against the target laid-down in 3.9 SDGs⁵⁸. Even solar farm installation biomass energy operation would affect the ecosystem because it would give leeway to cut wood and to utilize wetland⁵⁹ and it would undermine the target set in 6.6 SDGs. Even the use of renewable in marine system would cause negative impact on the targets to be achieved under 14SDGs. The studies done in this behalf have indicated that its use in marine system would result in habitat loss, collision risk noise and electromagnetic

⁵²The World Bank, *Access to electricity (% production)* (2019)

⁵³Armin Razmjoo A., Sumper A., Davarpanah A., *Energy sustainability analysis based on SDGs for developing countries*. *Energy Sources A.*, 42 (2020), PP. 1041-1056

⁵⁴*ibid*

⁵⁵Tugcu C.T., Tiwari A.K., *Does renewable and /or non-renewable energy consumption matter for total factor productivity (TFP) growth? Evidence from the BRICS*. *Renew. Sustain. Energy. Rev.*, 65 (2016), PP. 610-616

⁵⁶AL-Shetwi A. Q., Hannan M., Jern K.P., Mansur M., Mahlia T., *Grid-connected renewable energy sources: Review of the recent integration requirements and control methods*. *J. cleaner prod.*, 253 (2020), Article 119831

⁵⁷Liu W., Zhang X., Feng S. *Does renewable energy policy work? Evidence from a panel data analysis*. *Renew. Energy*, 2=135 (2019), PP 635-642

⁵⁸Freiberg A., Scharfe J., Murta V.G., Seidler A., *The use of biomass for electricity generation: A scoping review of health effects on humans in residential and occupational setting*. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 15 (2018), P. 354

⁵⁹Hamouda R.A., EL-Naggar NE-A., Doleib N.M., Saddiq A.A., *Bioprocessing strategies for cost-effective simultaneous removal of Chromium and Malachite green by marine alga Enteromorpha intestinalis*. *Sci. rep.*, 10(2020), PP. 1-9

harms⁶⁰. These effects would cause potential impact even on other coastal species particularly predators living in marine system⁶¹. An acidification to small extent is also caused during the time of construction, operation and also at the time of decommissioning of offshore wind energy and tidal energy⁶². Further wind energy would cause spatial tension in the life cycle of marine species such as fishes, aquatic mammals and birds⁶³.

CHALLENGES IN UTILIZATION OF RENEWABLE ENERGY IN THE ATTAINMENT OF SDGS

Even though there is a major global transformation for the integration of renewable energy with broader SDG framework, there are challenges in its progression. Each challenge presents a window of opportunity for innovation, stronger global partnership and rally around shared values for communities. The challenges being faced in this behalf are causing complexities in the pathways of renewable energy but they are mouldable with progressive steps to be initiated in this regard.

- 1) The initial capital required for adopting renewable energy technologies is very high. It becomes too heavy especially for developing countries which are striving to meet SDGs simultaneously.
- 2) Many countries at the world level lack expertise or technology required for harnessing renewable energy in their regions.
- 3) The countries are finding it harder to change their reliance from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources because communities living in it resist due to fear of losing the source of livelihood and uncertainty as to meeting of energy requirements by adoption of renewable solutions.
- 4) Policies being framed in some countries are not aligning with SDG targets. A compulsion to adopt renewable energy would disjoint with its already initiated efforts.

⁶⁰Hodges D.G., Chapagain B., Watcharaanantapong P., Poudyal N.G., Kline K.L., Dale V.H., Opportunities and attitudes of private forest landowners in supplying woody biomass for renewable energy. *Renew. Sustain. Energy. Rev.*, 113 (2019), Article 105205

⁶¹Inger R., Attrill M.J., Bearhop S., Broderick A.G., Grecian W. James, Hodgson D.J., et al. Marine renewable energy: Potential benefits to bio-diversity? An urgent call for research. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 46 (2009), PP. 1145-1153

⁶²Gill A.B., Offshore renewable energy: ecological implications of generating electricity in coastal zone. *J. Appl. Ecol.* (2005), PP. 605-615

⁶³Hagos K.W., Impact of Offshore Wind Energy on Marine Fisheries in Rhode Island: White paper in integrated coastal science

- 5) There are hurdles in the updating of infrastructure to implement renewable technologies. It has become a challenge in the implementation of renewable energy and a hesitancy as to causing of disruption in the established system in several countries. It requires large scale investment and man-power.

SUGGESTIONS FOR REMOVAL OF CHALLENGES IN UTILIZATION OF RENEWABLE ENERGY IN THE ATTAINMENT OF SDGS

There are opportunities and pathways to obviate the challenges falling in the ways of utilization of Renewable Energy in the attainment of SDGs.

- i. An encouragement for evolution or innovation of an affordable and efficient renewable energy sources will resolve the hurdle lying in adoption of renewable energy. The developed countries are to provide research and development assistance supportive to innovation of renewable energy technologies. At present, there are a few areas ripe for breakthrough such as solar panel efficiency, energy storage solutions and smart grids.
- ii. Countries which are leading renewable energy technologies are to provide expertise and resources to other countries which are in the course of adoption for renewable energy technologies. Platforms available in the form of United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) can be utilized to foster international collaboration. The global nature of the SDGs can be used to evolve international partnership in sharing of advanced technical knowledge concerning renewable energy utilization.
- iii. A campaign for local awareness to garner the support of communities towards the adoption of renewable energy is to be done sincerely. For it, the communities are to be engaged in grass roots initiatives involved in local solar or wind projects. They are to be made realised as to the direct benefits accruable from renewable energy such as job creation and cleaner air. They are to be catalysed as active proponents of change
- iv. It is necessary to evolve an innovative financing solution such as green bonds, public-private partnership and global funds dedicated to renewable energy. These initiatives are to be used to overcome the initial capital challenges. Already there exists Green Climate Fund (GCF) as a global initiative to assist developing nations in the path of their green energy transition. Further innovative technologies to be evolved need to

set right adversities being caused in the utilization of existing renewable energy technologies.

- v. The intricate inter play existing between renewable energy and SDGs are to be sorted-out by proper policies harmonising it. A policy being introduced to promote agro-solar projects is not only addressing targets set 7th goal of SDG (Cleanliness) but it is addressing goal set in 2 SDGs (zero hunger)

CONCLUSION

A prominent element understandable from the analytical observation is that sustainable developments are deeply intertwined with energy choices. A discussion in the realm of utilization of renewable energy makes it unequivocally clear that the essence of renewable energy resonates profound with the ambitions of the global sustainable development agenda. The synergy that one finds in intertwining relationship existing between them is not just incidental but fundamental in nature.

A true flourishing of renewable energy utilization will take place only when policy makers, stakeholders and individual will beckon their active participation. It does not survive by mere recognition; it requires indelible acknowledgement as to its necessity for the future life.

A world as a whole has to move from the depth of blue carbon to the vast expanse of green energy. Sustainability is not a transitory element; it is an intricate cogwheel with disparate teeth but fits perfectly together for holistic cause of the world. Whatever obstacles found in the combined journey of sustainable development and renewable energy are to be sorted-out with a positive note as to its enablement than its inhibitors.